

1 **Time Course Production of Urolithins from Ellagic acid by Human Gut**

2 **Microbiota**

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10 **ABSTRACT**

11 Ellagic acid (EA) is converted to urolithins by gut microbiota. Urolithins have
12 beneficial biological effects in humans but differences in urolithin production capacity
13 among individuals have been shown. Therefore, the identification of the urolithin
14 production pathways and the microorganisms implicated is of high interest. EA was
15 incubated with gut microbiota from two volunteers able to produce urolithins but with
16 different *in vivo* urolithin profiles (urolithin A and isourolithin A producers). The
17 metabolic capabilities observed *in vivo*, were retained *in vitro*. Both individuals showed
18 a much higher abundance of *Clostridium leptum* group of Firmicutes phylum than
19 *Bacteroides/Prevotella*. EA was either dissolved in DMSO or suspended in water. DMSO
20 increased EA solubility but decreased urolithin production rate, due to a delay in growth
21 of some microbial groups principally, *Clostridium coccooides*. This allowed the detection
22 of catabolic intermediates [urolithins M-5, M-6, M-7, C and 2,3,8,10-tetrahydroxy
23 urolithin (urolithin E)]. Bacteria from *C. coccooides* group (or genera co-occurring *in vivo*
24 with this group), seem to be involved in production of different urolithins.

25 **KEYWORDS:** *ellagitannins, colon microbiota, metabolism, dibenzopyranones,*
26 *polyphenols, human health*

27 INTRODUCTION

28 Ellagitannins and ellagic acid (EA) are plant secondary metabolites that have relevant
29 antioxidant activities *in vitro*, potential cardiovascular protection and anticarcinogenic
30 and anti-inflammatory effects.¹⁻³ These phytochemicals are relevant constituents in
31 different foods including pomegranates, berries (strawberry, raspberry, blackberry, camu-
32 camu, etc.), nuts (walnuts, acorns, chestnuts, etc.), muscadine grapes, oak-aged wines,
33 and medicinal plants and tisanes (geranium, oak leaves, etc.). They are not absorbed in
34 the gut and are metabolized *in vivo* by the gut microbiota to produce a series of
35 metabolites known as urolithins.^{4,5} Therefore, urolithins have been suggested as
36 biomarkers of intake for strawberries, raspberries, pomegranates, walnuts and oak-aged
37 red wines.⁶ We have previously suggested that urolithins, that are much better absorbed
38 than the original ellagitannins, could be responsible for the systemic biological effects of
39 ellagitannins.^{2,5} Additional evidence supports this suggestion as urolithins and their
40 glucuronide and sulfate metabolites have shown relevant effects at the concentrations
41 found *in vivo*.⁷⁻⁹ Urolithins share a nucleus of a dibenzo-pyran-one, with different
42 hydroxyl substitutions. The first reported urolithins were urolithin A and urolithin B that
43 were found in kidney stones of sheep.¹⁰ In a recent study, it has been demonstrated that
44 other mammals also produce urolithins from ellagitannins, although they have different
45 structures and different hydroxylation patterns on the urolithin nucleus.¹¹ Thus,
46 isourolithin A has been found as the main *in vivo* metabolite in beef cattle after oak leaf
47 intake,¹² and a series of tetrahydroxy and trihydroxy urolithin metabolites were produced
48 by rats after *Geranium* extracts intake.¹³

49 Recently, it has been reported that some humans are able to produce isourolithin A as
50 the main *in vivo* metabolite instead of urolithin A after the intake of strawberries¹⁴ and
51 raspberries.¹⁵ Furthermore, marked person-to-person differences have been observed in

52 the level of *in vivo* urolithin production following consumption of ellagitannin-containing
53 food. *In vitro* anaerobic metabolism of EA to urolithin A in human fecal suspensions has
54 also been reported.¹⁶ More recently, *in vitro* anaerobic incubation of EA with human fecal
55 suspensions demonstrated conversion to some other urolithins, urolithins B, C and
56 isourolithin A.¹⁷ However, neither comparison between the *in vitro* and the *in vivo*
57 urolithin patterns of these volunteers nor their endogenous microbiota has been analyzed
58 in any of these studies.

59 In the present study we evaluated the *in vitro* time course production of urolithins
60 from EA by human fecal microbiota, from two volunteers who have urolithin A and
61 isourolithin A urinary excretion patterns. Detailed *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments were
62 performed to identify the intermediary and final catabolites of EA conversion by the
63 human gut microbiota, to elucidate interindividual urolithin production routes and to
64 determine if EA metabolism could be linked to the microbiota composition of these
65 individuals.

66

67 MATERIALS AND METHODS

68 **Chemicals.** EA and 6,7-dihydroxycoumarin were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St.
69 Louis, MO, USA). Urolithins A and B were chemically synthesized by Villapharma S.L.
70 (Parque Tecnológico de Fuente Álamo, Murcia, Spain). Urolithins C (3,7,8-tetrahydroxy-
71 6H-dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one, Uro-C; > 95% purity) and D (2,3,7,8-tetrahydroxy-6H-
72 dibenzo[*b,d*]pyran-6-one, Uro-D; > 95% purity) were purchased from Dalton Pharma
73 Services (Toronto, Canada). Methanol and acetonitrile were purchased from Romil
74 (Barcelona, Spain) and ethyl acetate and dimethyl sulfoxide from Labscan (Dublin,
75 Ireland). Formic acid and hydrochloric acid was obtained from Panreac (Barcelona,

76 Spain). Milli-Q system (Millipore Corp., Bedford, MA) ultrapure water was used
77 throughout this experiment. Nutrient broth (NB) was from Oxoid (Basingstoke,
78 Hampshire, UK). L-cysteine hydrochloride was from (Panreac química, Barcelona, Spain).
79 Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was from (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain). All chemicals and
80 reagents used in the preparation of buffers, macromineral, micromineral and reducing
81 solutions were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Panreac and Scharlab.

82 **Collection of human fecal samples.** These were donated by a healthy female
83 (age 31) and a healthy male (age 36) in the Centro de Edafología y Biología Aplicada del
84 Segura (CEBAS-CSIC, Murcia, Spain). These two volunteers were identified as urolithin
85 A and isourolithin A producers respectively, in a previous study in which urine samples
86 were analyzed after the intake of strawberries and strawberry jam ^(paper by Truchado et al., 2012),
87 although these metabolic groups were not reported. To conduct fermentation experiments
88 in duplicate, each volunteer donated 2 fecal samples. They were stored at 4 °C and were
89 further processed within 1 h of donation as no differences in microbial concentrations
90 were observed in fresh samples before and after processing samples for fermentation
91 experiments. Anoxic conditions were maintained by using the AnaerobeGen compact
92 system (Oxoid).

93 **Fermentation Medium.** This was prepared as described by Jaganath et al. ¹⁸ with
94 some modifications. Briefly, 2 g of tryptone, 2 g glucose, 1 g maltose and 2 g yeast extract
95 were mixed in 400 mL of distilled water and 100 µL of micromineral solutions (consisting
96 of 13.2 g of CaCl₂·2H₂O, 10 g of MnCl₂·4H₂O, 1 g of CoCl₂·6H₂O, 8 g of FeCl₃·6H₂O,
97 and distilled water up to 100 mL), 200 mL of buffer solution (2 g of NH₃CO₃, 17.5 g
98 Na₂CO₃, and distilled water up 500 mL), 200 mL of macromineral solution (2.85 g of
99 NA₂HPO₄, 3.1 g KH₂PO₄, 0.3 g MgSO₄·7H₂O, and distilled water up to 500 mL), 1 mL
100 of 1% (w/v) of resazurin solution (a redox indicator) and 0.5 mg/L of Vit K₁, 5 mg/L and

101 625 mg/L haemin. The medium was adjusted to pH 7 using HCl, dispensed into the
102 fermentation vessels and autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min and allowed to cool under
103 oxygen-free nitrogen (OFN) to remove oxygen.

104 **Conversion experiments of EA into urolithins with human fecal cultures.**

105 Preparation of fecal suspensions and subsequent culturing experiments were conducted
106 under anoxic conditions in an anaerobic chamber (Don Whitley Scientific Limited,
107 Shipley, UK) with an atmosphere consisting of N₂/H₂/CO₂ (80 : 10 : 10) at 37 °C. Aliquots
108 of fecal samples (10 g) were diluted 1/10 (w/v) in NB supplemented with 0.05% L-
109 cysteine hydrochloride and homogenized by stomacher in filter bags. Aliquots of filtered
110 fecal suspensions (2 mL) were inoculated into 200 mL pre-reduced fermentation medium
111 containing EA at 30 µM with and without 1% DMSO. DMSO was used in order to
112 increase EA solubility and EA dissolved in water instead of DMSO was used as control.
113 Duplicate cultures were prepared in parallel from each fecal suspension. In addition,
114 controls were used; ones without fecal suspension and others without EA. Samples (6
115 mL) were collected at appropriate time intervals during 8 day incubation at 37 °C and
116 stored at -20 °C until further HPLC and qPCR analysis.

117 **Sample clean-up for LC analyses.** Feces and urine of the two volunteers were
118 extracted and analyzed. Urine samples were defrosted, vortexed and centrifuged at 14,000
119 x g for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was filtered through 0.45 µm PVDF filter and
120 analyzed by HPLC-DAD-IT MS. When the intensity was not enough to distinguish the
121 metabolites, urine samples were concentrated using a Sep-Pak reverse phase C-18
122 extraction cartridge (Waters Millipore). The cartridges were previously activated with 10
123 mL of MeOH and 10 mL of water. 25 mL of urine acidified with 250 µL formic acid (1%)
124 were passed through the cartridge that was then dried with air. The metabolites remaining
125 in the cartridge were eluted with 3 mL of MeOH/H₂O (50/50, v/v). Samples were

126 analyzed after filtration through 0.45 μ m PVDF filter. Feces samples (1 g) were defrosted
127 and homogenized with 10 mL of MeOH:DMSO:H₂O (40:40:20) with 0.1% HCl using an
128 Ultra-Turrax for 1 min at 24,000 rpm. The mixture was centrifuged at 5,000 x g for 10
129 min at room temperature and the supernatant filtered through a 0.45 μ m PVDF filter
130 before analysis.

131 Samples (5 mL) obtained in fermentation experiments with human faecal suspensions
132 were extracted with 5 mL of ethyl acetate acidified with 1.5% formic acid. The mixture
133 was vortexed for 2 min and centrifuged at 3500 x g for 10 min. The organic phase was
134 separated and evaporated under reduced pressure until dryness. The dry samples were
135 then redissolved in 250 μ L of methanol and filtered through a 0.45 μ m PVDF filter. Five
136 μ L of 100 μ g/mL of internal standard (6,7-dihydroxycoumarin) was added to 50 μ L of
137 sample prior to the injection onto a column for LC-UV/Vis and LC-MS analysis under
138 the conditions described below.

139 **LC-UV/Vis and LC-MS/MS analyses.** The analyses were performed using an
140 Agilent 1100 HPLC system equipped with a photodiode-array detector and an ion-
141 trap mass spectrometer detector in series (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany).
142 Chromatographic separation was carried out on a reverse phase LiChroCART C-18
143 column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (250 x 4 mm, 4.5 μ m particle size) using water
144 with 1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B) as the mobile phases. The gradient profile
145 was: 0-20 min, 5-30% B, 20-30 min, 30-55% B, 30-38 min, 55-90% B, this percentage
146 was maintained for 2 minutes and then came back to the initial conditions. A volume of
147 10 μ L of sample was injected onto the column operating at room temperature and a flow
148 rate of 1 mL/min. UV chromatograms were recorded at 280, 360 and 305 nm.

149 The HPLC system was coupled in series to an ion trap mass spectrometer (IT)
150 equipped with an electrospray interface (ESI). Nitrogen was used as drying gas with flow

151 of 11 L/min and temperature of 350 °C and nebulising gas at pressure of 65 psi. The
152 capillary voltage was set at 4 kV. Mass scan (MS) and daughter (MS-MS) spectra were
153 recorded in negative mode in the range of m/z 100-700 with target mass of 300. Maximum
154 accumulation time of ion trap and the number of MS repetitions to obtain the MS average
155 spectra were set at 200ms and 3, respectively. Compound stability was set at 75%.

156 Identification of all metabolites was carried out by direct comparison (UV spectra and
157 MS) with pure standards and confirmed by their spectral properties and molecular mass.
158 Calibration curves were obtained for EA, urolithin A, urolithin B and urolithin C with
159 good linearity ($R^2 > 0.998$). EA was quantified at 360 nm and urolithins at 305 nm. The
160 limits of detection (LODs) were determined based on a signal to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3
161 and of 10 for the limit of quantification (LOQ). EA, urolithin A and urolithin B showed
162 LODs of 0.5 μ M and LOQs of 1.67 μ M and urolithin C, LOD of 0.2 μ M and LOQ of
163 0.67 μ M. Repeatability was evaluated injecting 20 μ M of a mixture of standards four
164 times in the same day (intraday repeatability) and in four different days (interday
165 repeatability). The results expressed as the relative standard deviation (RSD) of peak area
166 were $\leq 5\%$ for intraday repeatability and $\leq 8\%$ for inter-day repeatability. The recovery
167 of the compounds was calculated spiking the medium in the presence of inactivated
168 bacteria with a standard solution of EA, urolithin A and urolithin B in DMSO at final
169 concentration of 20 μ M. Recoveries of 75%, 90% and 83% were obtained for EA,
170 urolithin A and urolithin B respectively. Isourolithin A was quantified at 305 nm with the
171 urolithin A calibration curve and urolithins M-5, M-6 and M-7 at 360 nm with the EA
172 calibration curve.

173 **Fecal dry weight determination and DNA extraction.** To determine fecal
174 moisture content, approximately 0.5 g (wet weight) of each fecal specimen was placed in
175 a vacuum dryer for 3 d and re-weighed. Percent fecal dry weight was calculated. Total

176 DNA was extracted from human fecal samples using a commercial DNA extraction kit
177 (QIAampR DNA Stool Mini Kit, Qiagen Inc., Valencia, CA). Although this kit did not
178 contain beads, an additional step of vigorous shaking using the FastPrep® Instrument was
179 carried out. Briefly, 10 mg of fresh fecal samples ($25.3\pm 8.9\%$ dry matter) were added to
180 2 mL tubes containing specialized beads (MP Biomedicals, LLC, Ohio, USA) and
181 homogenized in the lysing matrix using the FastPrep® Instrument for 30 seconds at a
182 speed setting of 5.5. Following steps were carried out attending protocol supplied with
183 the kit: incubation temperatures (95 °C, 5 min and 70 °C, 10 min); cell lysis and
184 homogenization (centrifugation at 14,000 rpm, 1 min); adsorption of inhibitors (InhibitEx
185 tablet); approximate time to completion (60 to 80 min).

186 **Real-time qPCR.** DNA from dominant groups of fecal bacteria was quantified with
187 real-time qPCR and primers as summarized in **Table 1**. Real-time qPCR was performed
188 using an ABI 7500 Sequence Detection System. Amplification and detection were carried
189 out in 96-well plates with TaqMan® Universal PCR 2 x Master Mix (Applied-
190 Biosystems) or with SYBR-Green® PCR 2 x Master Mix (Applied-Biosystems). Each
191 reaction was run in duplicate in a final volume of 25 µL with 0.2 mM final concentration
192 of each primer, 0.25 mM final concentration of each probe and 10 mL of appropriate
193 dilutions of DNA samples. Probes were designed with Molecular-Groove Binding Non-
194 fluorescence Quencher (MGBNFQ). Amplifications were carried out using the following
195 ramping profile: 1 cycle at 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s, 60
196 °C for 1 min. For SYBR-Green amplifications, a melting step was added in order to check
197 the expected amplification products.

198 When PCR was performed on unknown fecal samples, the cycle threshold of each
199 sample was compared with a standard curve (performed in triplicate) made by diluting
200 genomic DNA (6-fold serial dilution of *Bifidobacterium longum* DSM 20088^T for

201 *Bifidobacterium* genus; *Escherichia coli* CECT 515^T for *E. coli* species; *Clostridium*
202 *leptum* DSM 753^T and *Clostridium coccooides* DSM 935^T for *C. leptum* and *C. coccooides*
203 groups, *Bacteroides ovatus* DSM 1896^T for *Bacteroides/Prevotella* group and
204 *Lactobacillus plantarum* CECT 748^T for *Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus* group).
205 Selected bacteria strains were cultured anaerobically on selective broth as recommended
206 by DSMZ. For each culture, the total number of bacteria, in terms of CFU, was
207 determined by plating. Aliquots of 1 mL of culture were used for DNA extraction by
208 DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Quiagen) following the manufacturer's instructions.

209 **Statistical Analyses and Data modeling.** Fecal samples were analyzed in
210 triplicate and the quantitative estimates represent mean values \pm standard error. Data were
211 subjected to statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA). Normality of variances was tested
212 by Shapiro-Wilk test, before determining the ANOVA. Statistical analyses were
213 performed using SPSS V.14 for Windows.

214 Microbial growth curves were fitted using the function of Baranyi et al.¹⁹ to estimate
215 the main growth parameters (maximum specific growth rate, lag time of microorganisms
216 before the onset of growth and estimated correlation coefficient, that indicates the
217 goodness of fit of the parameters derived from experimental data). Only growth curves
218 with at least 10 data points were used for modeling, as suggested by the authors.

219

220 **RESULTS**

221 ***In vivo* metabolism of EA and ellagitannins by human gut microbiota.** Two
222 volunteers who had different routes of EA metabolism *in vivo* were selected for the
223 present study. Volunteer 1 produced urolithin A and volunteer 2 produced isourolithin A.
224 We had previously identified these two urolithin metabolic profile groups in urine

225 samples from different volunteers after the intake of walnuts, strawberries and raspberries
226 (unpublished data). The analyses of fecal samples from both volunteers after the intake
227 of walnuts (0.6 g/kg body weight per day for 5 days) showed that volunteer 1 had a
228 chromatographic profile characterized by urolithin A that was identified by its MS
229 spectrum, its characteristic UV spectrum ¹¹ and by chromatographic comparisons with an
230 authentic standard, while volunteer 2 produced isourolithin A as a main metabolite
231 (**Figure 1**). The UV spectra of urolithin A and isourolithin A allow a clear and fast
232 identification of both metabolites ¹¹. In addition other minor metabolites were also
233 detected in fecal samples of both volunteers [urolithin M-6 (**7**) and urolithin C (**8**)] (**Table**
234 **2**). When the urine of the same volunteers was analyzed, their metabolic profiles were
235 consistent with those found in feces, and volunteer 1 excreted mainly urolithin A
236 glucuronide (**1**), while volunteer 2 excreted two isomers of isourolithin A glucuronide (**2**,
237 **3**) instead (**Figure 2**). Trace amounts of urolithin B-glucuronide (**10**) were also detected
238 in the urine of volunteer 2 (**Figure 2B**).

239 **Bacterial populations of human fecal samples used in this study.** Fecal
240 bacteria densities of the two volunteers, who donated feces for the investigation of the
241 metabolic fate of EA *in vivo*, were also analyzed. Interindividual differences in fecal
242 microbiota were analyzed by qRT-PCR using primers and probes (**Table 1**) that target
243 the main bacterial groups: *Bifidobacterium* genus; *C. leptum* group (*C. leptum*,
244 *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and some species of *Ruminococcus* genus); *C. coccoides*
245 group (*C. coccoides*., *Eubacterium rectale spp.* and some species of *Ruminococcus*
246 genus); *E. coli* species; *Bacteroides/Prevotella* group;
247 *Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus* group (**Table 1**). All-bacteria results were
248 presented as the mean of the log CFU per g feces. Fecal dry weight (%) was 31.7 and

249 19.0% in volunteers 1 and 2. To overcome the fact that fecal samples contained different
250 water, a correction factor ($19/31.7=0.6$) was applied to microbial data of volunteer 1.

251 Fecal sample analyses from both urolithin A (volunteer 1) and isourolithin A
252 (volunteer 2) producers were analyzed (**Figure 3**). This study showed that one of the most
253 highly represented bacterial groups, in human stools of both volunteers, was the *C. leptum*
254 group of the Firmicutes phylum. No significant differences in levels of *C. leptum* group
255 ($7-34 \times 10^7$ CFU/g) and *C. coccoides* group ($5-8 \times 10^6$ CFU/g) of the Firmicutes phylum
256 as well as *Bacteroides/Prevotella* group ($5-12 \times 10^5$ CFU/g) of the Bacteroidetes phylum
257 were observed between fecal samples from volunteers 1 and 2. However, concentrations
258 of other bacterial groups in volunteer 1 fecal sample were noticeably different from those
259 of volunteer 2 fecal sample ($P \leq 0.01$) (**Figure 3**). Thus, the microbiota from volunteer 1
260 showed a higher concentration of *Bifidobacterium* genus (6×10^8 CFU/g) of the
261 Actinobacteria phylum when compared with that of volunteer 2 (1×10^6 log CFU/g)
262 (**Figure 3A**). Furthermore, in volunteer 1, the fecal sample contained a higher
263 concentration of *E. coli* species (1×10^6 CFU/g) of the Proteobacteria phylum than fecal
264 sample of volunteer 2 (8×10^4 CFU/g). In contrast, lower abundance of
265 *Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus* group of the Firmicutes phylum was found in
266 volunteer 1 (2×10^4 CFU/g) which were 2.7 log units lower than counts for fecal sample
267 of volunteer 2 (1×10^7 CFU/g) (**Figure 3**). These studies showed that the most highly
268 represented bacterial group in volunteer 2 was the *C. leptum* of the Firmicutes phylum
269 while *C. leptum* and *Bifidobacterium* genus of the Firmicutes and Actinobacteria phyla
270 were the major representative in volunteer 1.

271 ***In vitro* catabolism of EA by human gut microbiota.** The production of
272 urolithins by the gut microbiota from the two volunteers was followed *in vitro* in order to
273 study the time course of the production of the two microbial metabolite patterns found *in*

274 *in vivo* and identify potential intermediate catabolites in the route from EA to urolithin A or
275 isourolithin A (**Figure 4**). The first metabolites observed when EA was incubated with
276 the volunteer 1 (urolithin A producer) fecal microbiota were urolithin M-5
277 (pentahydroxy-urolithin) and urolithin M-6 (tetrahydroxy-urolithin) which peaked at 12
278 h with a maximum concentration of 1 and 2.5 μM respectively (**Figure 4A**). Then,
279 urolithin C (trihydroxy-urolithin) started to be accumulated reaching 9.4 μM at 14 h. At
280 that moment, a small amount of another trihydroxy-urolithin (urolithin M-7) started to be
281 produced with a maximum of 0.29 μM at 16 h. Urolithin A was detected after 14 h
282 incubation and a maximum of 19.6 μM was reached at 42 h, then a plateau was maintained
283 (**Figure 4A**). A large proportion of the EA supplied (30 μM) was finally converted into
284 urolithin A (21 μM), although some EA remained un-metabolized in the medium (1.3
285 μM).

286 In the case of volunteer 2 (isourolithin A producer), no urolithin M-5 was detected
287 and both urolithin C and urolithin M-6 appeared with a maximum after 5 hours (7.5 and
288 3.5 μM respectively) (**Figure 4B**). Then isourolithin A started to be produced reaching a
289 maximum of 10 μM after 24 hours. Isourolithin A then decreased, and urolithin B
290 increased to reach 6.5 μM after 60 hours and then reached a plateau. At the same time as
291 urolithin B was produced, some urolithin A was also observed, although it reached
292 concentrations much lower than those found for volunteer 1 (3 μM). The maximum EA
293 conversion to urolithins was lower in the case of volunteer 2 fecal fermentation (15 μM)
294 (**Figure 4B**) than in the case of volunteer 1 fecal fermentation (21 μM) (**Figure 4A**) and
295 some EA remained un-metabolized in the medium (2 μM).

296 The urolithin production from EA when this was dissolved in DMSO and added to
297 the fermentation medium (1%) to increase its solubility, and potentially its bacterial

298 accessibility, was also evaluated. The EA catabolism was very different from that
299 observed when EA was added to the fermentation medium without adding any organic
300 solvent and significant changes were observed in growth parameters of some bacterial
301 groups analyzed as described in the section below. In the case of volunteer 1, the main *in*
302 *vitro* metabolite produced in the presence of DMSO was urolithin M-5 (pentahydroxy-
303 urolithin) instead of urolithin A, which started to be detected after 12 h, with a maximum
304 concentration of 9 μM at 40 h incubation. Urolithin M-6, urolithin M-7 and urolithin A
305 were also observed but not before 16, 36 and 42 h incubation respectively and in much
306 smaller maximal concentrations (0.3, 1.3 and 0.5 μM , respectively) (**Figure 4C**) than in
307 the absence of DMSO (2.5, 0.3 and 19.6 μM , respectively) (**Figure 4A**). Urolithin C was
308 not produced in the presence of DMSO (**Figure 4C**). Despite the smaller and slower
309 urolithin production in presence of the DMSO, a large proportion of EA supplied was
310 metabolized in the medium (24 μM) (**Figure 4C**). A relevant unidentified tetrahydroxy
311 urolithin was started to be produced after 36 h of incubation, and this was named as
312 urolithin E (**Figure 4C**). This had the same mass spectrum as urolithin M-6. In order to
313 identify the structure of urolithin E this was compared with the other two available
314 tetrahydroxy-urolithins, urolithin D and urolithin M-6. All of them had the same MS
315 spectrum, but differed in the UV spectrum (**Figure 5**). Urolithin M-6 had a characteristic
316 UV spectrum, and urolithin D had a similar spectrum to urolithin A. Urolithin E, had a
317 different UV spectrum, with a significant band I at 360 nm, a characteristic of those
318 urolithins without a hydroxyl at 9-position (**Figure 5**).¹¹ Therefore urolithin E was
319 tentatively identified as 3,4,8,10-tetrahydroxy-urolithin, a new urolithin metabolite. NMR
320 analysis of this urolithin was not possible due to the small amount produced.

321 In the case of volunteer 2, when EA added was dissolved in DMSO, this started to be
322 converted to urolithin M-5, urolithin M-6 and urolithin C with a maximum concentration

323 of 2, 6 and 7.5 μM after 7.5, 10 and 25 hours, respectively. Then urolithin A started to be
324 produced reaching a maximum (22 μM) after 40 hours (**Figure 4D**). In this case only
325 small concentration of isourolithin A was detected (1 μM). Urolithin M-7 was also
326 observed and reached maximal concentrations of 3 μM after 50 hours. Most EA was
327 metabolized and only low concentrations (1 μM) remained un-metabolized in the medium
328 (**Figure 4D**).

329 **Changes in human gut microbiota *in vitro*.** Changes in the fecal microbiota of
330 volunteers 1 and 2 were followed during the *in vitro* metabolism of EA in order to
331 elucidate which microbial groups could be implicated in the production of urolithins. The
332 growth characteristics of the main bacterial groups, determined by q-PCR, during the
333 conversion of EA *in vitro* batch fermentation are shown in **Table 3**. In absence of DMSO,
334 the main differences between fecal microbiota development of volunteers 1 and 2 were
335 detected in the *Bifidobacterium* genus. In fact, the bifidobacteria of volunteer 2 were not
336 able to grow in the *in vitro* conditions despite urolithins being produced.
337 *Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus* group also grew slower in volunteer 2 than in
338 volunteer 1 but a higher level of bacteria was obtained at the end of the growth (N_{max})
339 in volunteer 2 (5.0 log CFU/mL) than in volunteer 1 culture (4.4 log CFU/mL). In
340 contrast, *C. coccoides* group reached a higher level in volunteer 1 (N_{max} : 6.1 log
341 CFU/mL) than in volunteer 2 culture (N_{max} : 5.0 log CFU/mL) (**Table 3**). In the same
342 way, urolithin concentrations were higher in volunteer 1 than in volunteer 2 culture.

343 In the presence of DMSO, a delay in the growth of *C. coccoides* group was observed
344 in both volunteer fecal fermentations. Thus, the lag period was extended in 9.7 and 22
345 hours in the case of volunteers 1 and 2, respectively (**Table 3**). For human fecal
346 suspensions of volunteer 1, the extension of the lag phase in 9.7 hours of *C. coccoides*

347 group in presence of DMSO was accompanied by a delay of 10 hours in the beginning of
348 urolithin production. A similar tendency was observed in fecal suspension of volunteer 2
349 where the presence of DMSO lengthen both lag period (24.6 hours) and time needed to
350 achieve the maximum urolithin concentration. In contrast, the *Bacteroides/Prevotella*
351 group achieved higher levels in the absence of DMSO (Nmax: 7.2 log CFU/mL) than
352 when DMSO was present (Nmax: 6.8 log CFU/mL) in the case of volunteer 2 (**Table 3**).

353

354 **DISCUSSION**

355 The studies carried out so far with human biological fluids (urine and plasma) have
356 allowed the identification of urolithin A, urolithin B, urolithin C and isourolithin A.⁵
357 Other metabolites such as urolithins M-5, M-6 and M-7 had been reported in rat fecal
358 samples and other animal materials.¹¹⁻¹³ However, this is the first time that urolithin M-
359 5, urolithin M-6, urolithin M-7, urolithin C and the new identified metabolite urolithin E
360 are reported to be produced by human gut microbiota. Urolithin M-6 (tetrahydroxy-
361 urolithin) was detected with a maximum concentration between those of urolithin M-5
362 and two trihydroxy-urolithins (urolithin C and urolithin M-7) as could be expected for the
363 catabolic sequence (**Figure 6**). This shows that these metabolites occur *in vivo* in human
364 gut, although they can be quickly metabolized into urolithin A that is the main metabolite
365 found in plasma and urine. Analysis of human feces after the intake of ellagitannins and
366 EA should be carried out in order to evaluate the occurrence of these urolithin metabolites
367 in the gut conditions after the intake of EA containing foods where other food constituents
368 such as fiber could influence either the EA availability or gut microbial populations.

369 Degradation of EA by human gut microbiota leads to similar urolithin metabolites *in*
370 *vitro* (fermentation medium containing EA at 30 μ M) than *in vivo* (after consumption of

371 0.6 g walnuts /kg body weight per day for 5 days). Thus, both urolithin A and isourolithin
372 A producers *in vivo* (volunteers 1 and 2), led to urolithin A and isourolithin A *in vitro*,
373 respectively (**Figures 4A** and **4B**). Despite urolithin metabolic profiles found *in vivo* were
374 consistent with those found *in vitro*, further studies should be done in order to study the
375 time course of the production of the two microbial metabolite patterns when EA
376 containing foods are used in place of EA. This would elucidate the influence of other food
377 constituents on urolithin production rate.

378 In the human fecal culture of volunteer 1 (*in vivo* urolithin A producer) EA was 62%
379 converted to urolithins at 36 hours while in volunteer 2 (*in vivo* isourolithin A producer)
380 the conversion efficiency to urolithins was much lower (46% at 36 h). Taking into account
381 the higher EA conversion efficiency of volunteer 1 and the fact that of *C. coccoides* group
382 achieved 1 log higher concentration in fecal fermentation sample of volunteer 1 than in
383 volunteer 2, this suggests that this microbial group or other *in vivo* co-occurring bacteria
384 could be involved in EA catabolism. In contrast, the lack of growth of *Bifidobacterium* in
385 volunteer 2 could indicate that this microbial group is not involved in urolithin
386 production.

387 Due to solubility problems of EA, this was alternatively dissolved in DMSO, and
388 incorporated into the medium at 1% v:v. In human fecal cultures where DMSO was
389 added, different EA conversion was observed (28% and 74% in the case of volunteer 1
390 and 2, respectively). In the case of volunteer 1, the EA catabolism did not reach the whole
391 transformation to urolithin A, and different intermediates were obtained. Urolithin M-5
392 was observed as the first step in urolithin production from EA, to continue with urolithin
393 M-6 and then urolithin M-7 to end with urolithin A but in much lower concentration than
394 in the absence of DMSO. Furthermore, the addition of DMSO prevented the conversion
395 of urolithin M-6 into urolithin C being one trihydroxy-urolithin (urolithin M-7) the only

396 precursor found for the final catabolite (uroolithin A) (**Figure 6**). Therefore, the use of
397 DMSO in fecal cultures, offered the possibility of studying other metabolic intermediates
398 between EA and urolithin A, such as urolithin E, another tetrahydroxy-uroolithin precursor
399 of urolithin M-7 (**Figure 6**). Despite the smaller urolithin production in presence of the
400 DMSO, most of the EA was metabolized in the medium (24 μ M). This indicates that
401 DMSO delayed urolithin producing bacteria development allowing the action of other
402 bacteria able to metabolize EA to simple organic acids such as phenyl acetic acid and
403 phenylpropionic acid. However, further studies should be done in order to elucidate if
404 higher abundance of Bacteroidetes and less abundance of Firmicutes such as *C. coccoides*
405 are correlated with a lower urolithin production *in vivo*.

406 In the case of human fecal culture of volunteer 2, it seems that the catabolic route of
407 EA to urolithins was modified by the effect of DMSO. In fact much lower concentration
408 of isourolithin A and much higher concentration of urolithin A were detected in presence
409 of DMSO (**Figure 4D**). This suggests that the microbial strains responsible for
410 isourolithin A production in volunteer 2 grew with difficulty under these *in vitro*
411 conditions. Furthermore, urolithin B was not detected which suggests isourolithin A and
412 not urolithin A is its only precursor and confirm this theory that was first proposed in
413 cattle after the administration of oak leaves.¹² In addition, this is also in agreement with
414 a previous *in vitro* study where urolithin B was only detected in those human fermentation
415 cultures where isourolithin A were detected.¹⁷ A negative effect of DMSO on the growth
416 of some bacterial groups was also observed, particularly, on *C. coccoides* bacteria. A
417 similar delay on growth of this bacterial group and the time needed to achieve the
418 maximum urolithin concentration was observed suggesting that this bacterial group could
419 be involved in the EA metabolism of both volunteers.

420 In the literature, nothing is found about bacterial species or groups responsible for
421 urolithin production from ellagitannins. In the present study, *C. coccoides* group (*C.*
422 *coccoides* spp., *E. rectale* spp. and some species of *Ruminococcus* genus) from Firmicutes
423 phylum, or genera co-occurring *in vivo* with this group, are proposed as the
424 microorganisms involved in urolithins production. *Clostridium* and *Eubacterium* genera
425 are a common element of the metabolism of several phenolic compounds such as
426 flavonoids.²⁰ Given the phylogenetic association between these two genera, the
427 association of them in the phenolic transformations is not surprising. The fecal samples
428 corresponding to *in vivo* urolithin A and isourolithin A producers showed a higher
429 abundance of either *C. coccoides* or *C. leptum* than that of the *Bacteroides/Prevotella*
430 group. Recently, three robust clusters, referred to as "enterotypes", which are not nation
431 or continent specific have been identified. Assignment of an individual microbiome into
432 a given enterotype is based upon the relative enrichment of that microbiome in one of
433 three genera: *Bacteroides* (enterotype 1), *Prevotella* (enterotype 2) or *Ruminococcus*
434 (enterotype 3).²¹ Further studies should be done in order to elucidate existent relations
435 between human urolithins production capacity and relative abundance of bacteria either
436 in the different phyla or in the different enterotypes.

437 Over the past decade there has been enormous public and scientific interest in
438 urolithins because of their proposed health-promoting effects, which, nonetheless, are far
439 from being fully understood.²² Future studies, should take the newly identified urolithin
440 metabolites into account when investigating EA absorption and metabolism as well as
441 their physiologic effects in humans. Isolation and identification of bacteria strains
442 implicated in urolithins production also require further investigation.

443

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449

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535 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

536 **Figure 1.** HPLC-UV analysis at 305 nm of fecal samples of volunteer 1 (A) and volunteer
537 2 (B) after the intake of walnuts (0.6 g/kg body weight per day for 5 days). (7) urolithin
538 M-6; (8) urolithin C; (11) isourolithin A; (12) urolithin A.

539 **Figure 2.** HPLC-UV analysis at 305 nm of urine samples of volunteer 1 (A) and volunteer
540 2 (B) after the intake of walnuts (0.6 g/kg body weight per day for 5 days). (2) urolithin
541 A glucuronide; (3) isourolithin A glucuronide; (10) urolithin B glucuronide.

542 **Figure 3.** Quantities of dominant groups of bacteria in fecal samples of volunteer 1 (A)
543 and volunteer 2 (B) as determined by real-time polymerase chain reaction. The mean
544 (\pm SD) counts from triplicate determinations (3 DNA samples isolated from the same
545 feces) were used to quantify the bacterial groups. (Bif) *Bifidobacterium* genus; (C. lep)
546 *Clostridium leptum* group; (C. coc/Eu) *Clostridium coccooides* group; (E. coli) *E. coli*
547 species; (Bac/Prev) *Bacteroides/Prevotella* group; (Lac/Leu/Pedio)
548 *Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus* group. **Significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) in
549 bacteria levels between volunteer 1 (A) and volunteer 2 (B).

550 **Figure 4.** *In vitro* conversion of EA during batch fermentation with human feces from
551 two volunteers. Human fecal cultures consisted of (A) volunteer 1 fecal suspension in
552 fermentation medium with 30 μ M EA; (B) volunteer 2 fecal suspension in fermentation
553 medium with 30 μ M EA; (C) volunteer 1 fecal suspension in fermentation medium with
554 30 μ M EA dissolved with 1% DMSO; (D) volunteer 2 fecal suspension in fermentation
555 medium with 30 μ M EA dissolved with 1% DMSO. Urolithin
556 M-5; Urolithin
557 C; Urolithin B.

558 **Figure 5.** UV spectra of the three tetrahydroxy urolithins ([M-H]⁻ m/z 259): urolithin D,
559 urolithin E and urolithin M-6.

560 **Figure 6.** Structures of the main urolithin metabolites detected and suggested catabolic
561 routes of formation by gut microbiota.

Table 1. Primer and probe sequences used for detection of main bacterial groups in human feces by quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction. ^aProbe sequences.

Target organism groups and species ²³	Primers and probes	Sequence 5'–3'	Refs
<i>Clostridium leptum</i> group	F_Clept 09	CCT TCC GTG CCG SAG TTA	23
<i>Clostridium leptum</i>	R_Clept 08	GAA TTA AAC CAC ATA CTC CAC TGC TT	
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	P_Clep 01 ^a	6FAM-CAC AATAAG TAA TCC ACC	
<i>Ruminococcus albus</i>			
<i>Bifidobacterium</i> genus	F_Bifid 09c	CGG GTG AGT AAT GCG TGA CC	23
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	R_Bifid 06	TGA TAG GAC GCG ACC CCA	
<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	P_Bifid ^a	6FAM-CTC CTG GAA ACG GGT G	
<i>Bifidobacterium infantis</i>			
<i>Clostridium coccooides</i> group	F_Ccoc 07	GAC GCC GCG TGA AGG A	23
<i>Clostridium coccooides</i>	R_Ccoc 14	AGC CCC AGC CTT TCA CAT C	
<i>Ruminococcus gnavus</i>	P_Erec482 ^a	VIC-CGG TAC CTG ACT AAG AAG	24
<i>Ruminococcus hansenii</i>			
<i>Eubacterium rectale</i>			
<i>Bacteroides/Prevotella</i> group	F_Bacter 11	CCT WCG ATG GAT AGG GGT T	23
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	R_Bacter 08	CAC GCT ACT TGG CTG GTT CAG	
<i>Bacteroides ovatus</i>	P_Bac303 ^a	VIC-AAG GTC CCC CAC ATT G	25
<i>Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron</i>			
<i>Bacteroides uniformis</i>			
<i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>			
<i>Bacteroides caccae</i>			
<i>Bacteroides eggerthii</i>			
<i>Prevotella oralis</i>			
<i>Prevotella buccae</i>			
<i>Prevotella albensis</i>			
<i>E. coli</i> species	E.coli F	CAT GCC GCG TGT ATG AAG AA	26
	E.coli R	CGG GTA ACG TCA ATG AGC AAA	
<i>Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus</i> group	F_Lacto 05	AGC AGT AGG GAA TCT TCC A	23
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	R_Lacto 04	CGC CAC TGG TGT TCY TCC ATA TA	
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus johnsonii</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>			
<i>Lactobacillus helvetic</i>			
<i>Pediococcus inopinatus</i>			
<i>Pediococcus parvulus</i>			
<i>Pediococcus cellicola</i>			
<i>Pediococcus acidilactici</i>			
<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>			
<i>Leuconostoc pseudomesenteroides</i>			

Table 2. Metabolites identified in urine (U), feces (F), fermentation medium incubated with human fecal suspensions in the presence of ellagic acid (FM) or in the presence of ellagic acid dissolved in 1% DMSO (FM-DMSO). sh-shoulder. *Internal standard (6,7-dihydroxycoumarin): [M-H]⁻ 177 and retention time: 11.52 min

No	Compounds	Volunteers	Origins	Rt (min)	[M-H] ⁻	λmax
1	Urolithin A glucuronide	1	U	15.75	403	246, 278, 303, 350
2	Isourolithin A glucuronide	2	U	15.52	403	255, 299sh, 325
3	Isourolithin A glucuronide	2	U	16.14	403	255, 299sh, 325
4	Urolithin M-5	1	FM & FM-DMSO	14.65	275	261, 292sh, 352
		2	FM-DMSO			
5	Urolithin E	1	FM-DMSO	16.55	259	252, 276sh, 365
6	Ellagic acid	1 & 2	FM & FM-DMSO	17.62	301	254, 300sh, 366
7	Urolithin M-6	1 & 2	F & FM & FM-DMSO	17.94	259	259, 291sh, 350
8	Urolithin C	1	F & FM	18.83	243	255, 304, 349
		2	F & FM & FM-DMSO			
9	Urolithin M-7	1	FM & FM-DMSO	20.49	243	250, 280sh, 367
		2	FM-DMSO			
10	Urolithin B glucuronide	2	U	20.56	387	249, 273, 297, 326
11	Isourolithin A	2	F & FM & FM-DMSO	23.06	227	256, 302, 329
12	Urolithin A	1	F & FM & FM-DMSO	24.11	227	246, 280, 305, 356
		2	FM & FM-DMSO			
13	Urolithin B	2	FM	28.21	211	249, 276, 301, 333

Table 3. Growth characteristics of main bacterial groups determined by q-PCR during conversion of ellagic acid *in vitro* batch fermentation with human fecal suspensions. Fecal cultures consisted of volunteer 1 and 2 fecal suspensions in fermentation medium with 30 μ M ellagic acid (EA) dissolved or not with 1% DMSO. Significant differences in growth without and with DMSO addition. *($P \leq 0.05$), ** ($P \leq 0.05$)

Microbial groups	Volunteer	Fermentation medium + EA	Lag time (hour)	Grmax (log CFU/hour)	Nmax (log CFU/mL)	Correlation coefficient (R ²)
<i>Clostridium coccooides</i> group	1	Without DMSO	0	0.12	6.08	0.99
		With DMSO	9.66**	0.05**	5.87	0.99
	2	Without DMSO	2.59	0.10	5.04	0.99
		With DMSO	24.60**	0.14	5.08	0.99
<i>Bifidobacterium</i> genus	1	Without DMSO	0	0.15	7.91	0.92
		With DMSO	0	0.10	7.93	0.83
	2	Without DMSO		No growth		-
		With DMSO		No growth		-
<i>Clostridium leptum</i> group	1	Without DMSO	0	0.07	6.89	0.95
		With DMSO	0	0.04**	6.60*	0.87
	2	Without DMSO	0	0.11	7.08	0.99
		With DMSO	0	0.09	7.12	0.97
<i>Lactobacillus/Leuconostoc/Pediococcus</i>	1	Without DMSO	0	0.16	4.40	0.99
		With DMSO	0	0.18	4.34	0.99
	2	Without DMSO	0	0.02	5.00	0.99
		With DMSO	0	0.05**	4.96	0.99
<i>Bacteroides/Prevotella</i> group	1	Without DMSO	0	0.12	6.40	0.96
		With DMSO	0	0.24**	6.41	0.98
	2	Without DMSO	0	0.21	7.17	0.99
		With DMSO	0	0.21	6.81*	0.99
<i>E. coli</i> species	1	Without DMSO	0	0.45	8.22	0.98
		With DMSO	0	0.40	8.30	0.99
	2	Without DMSO	0	0.31	7.37	0.99
		With DMSO	0	0.27	7.83*	0.99

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

